

THE ROLE OF UNDERPRICING IN STOCK RETURN DETERMINANTS

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Abstract

This study is intended to conduct an analysis and answer the presence of research gaps that occur among researchers as well as the phenomena that occur where stock returns as a problem that needs to be carried out using underpricing as an intervening variable. This type of research is a quantitative descriptive with multiple regression analysis methods that use the object of research companies that conduct initial public offering (IPOS) with underpricing results listed in the Indonesia Stock Exchange. By using the Purposive Sampling method obtained the number of cross sections as many as thirty-five companies that were observed in this study and with time series for 5 years. Furthermore, this study produced a maximization of stock returns through underpricing. This study uses the approach of two research models that are integrated into one and each through the stages of the model selection test, namely the Chow Test, the Hausman Test. The results of research in the first model that uses the endogenous undergenerating variable with the results of all exogenous variables can significantly explain their effect on the endogenic variable and with the highest level of sensitivity in the earnings management variable. The results of the second model research using stock return as an endogenous variable with the result that all exogenous variables can also explain their effect significantly on the endogenic variable and with the highest level of sensitivity in the underpricing variable. These results are expected to help as a guideline for public companies to get market appreciation that is proxied into stock returns.

Keywords: Earnings Management, Under-pricing, Stock Return.

INTRODUCTION DAN LITERATURE REVIEW

The stock price sold in the prime market (IPOs) is determined based on an agreement between the issuer and the Underwriter, while the price in the secondary market is determined by the market mechanism (demand and supply). If the determination of stock prices when the IPOs is significantly lower than the prices that occur in the secondary market on the first day, then this incident is often called underpricing.

In line with the analysis of the stock underpricing level, there are some questions that are always raised, are: What is the consideration of the setting of the initial price of shares for issuers and underwriters? Why do you occur mispricing? Is the investor also determine the initial share price? To answer these questions, it is necessary to know the mechanism for determining the prime price of the first stock until the occurrence of mispriced.

There are three parties involved in setting stock prices in the primary market, namely issuers, underwriters and investors. Before shares were offered to the public, negotiations occurred between issuers and underwriters. The purpose of the issuer to do an IPOs at the highest possible price. However, if the IPOs stock price is set too high, the risk is that the stock is likely not to sell all, on the contrary if the price of IPOs shares is sold too low, it is possible that the

target funds needed cannot be achieved. Conversely, underwriters, of course, in this case have better information about supply and demand for issuer stocks, compared to the issuer itself, will use this information to obtain an optimal agreement with the issuer regarding the price of IPOs shares that benefit him, and try to minimize the risk of buying IPO shares that are not sold at the lowest possible price.

One form of relationship between issuers and underwriters is that underwriters buy shares from issuers and resell to the public or investors. The issuer who issued shares sells to the underwriter with the offer price is reduced by spread as compensation and underwriter will bear the risk if in the end shares cannot be sold at the offer price. This procedure is called the Firm Commitment. As an alternative to the Firm Commitment is that the Best Effort Agreement which is a procedure commonly used in IPOs. In this case, Underwriters agree to help sell their shares to the public, underwriters play a role only as an intermediary between the public and issuers and do not bear the risk if the underwriter cannot sell issuer shares to the public at a bid price (Bodie et al., 2019).

In general the IPOs process begins with initial preparation and document preparation. Followed by the submission of a preliminary application for the recording of shares to the Indonesia Stock Exchange. After that, the process that needs to be carried out is the delivery of registration statements to OJK. The registration process is a public offering, or recording and trading shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The stages to conduct IPOs are the first issuer to set up shares and sell shares to the public through shareholder meetings (GMS), then select underwriters and other supporting professions such as: Notary, Appraisal, Auditors and Legal Consultants, then the issuer prepares a preliminary prospectus and submitting registration to the Financial Services Authority (OJK).

This preliminary prospectus is known as "red herring" (red herring) because there is a statement printed with red ink that the company is not trying to sell securities before registration is approved. If the statement is completed and approved by the OJK, then this statement is called the prospectus. At this time the price of securities to be offered to the public was announced. One of the important stages of IPOs in determining the stock price is the underwriter will go around (road show) to publish the sale of these shares in the near future to interested potential investors. There are two goals to be achieved when the underwriting does a road show. First to attract and provide information for investors about the shares offered. Second, to gather issuer and underwriting information about the stock price to be sold. With the road show, it is hoped that large investors who want to buy securities at the time of the initial offer (IPOs) notify their interest to the underwriter. This sign of interest or attention is called a book (reservation) and the potential investor collection process is called bookbuilding. Note to the Potential Investors provides valuable information for issuers because large-scale institutional investors often have extensive insights regarding market demand for shares and prospects of the company concerned along with their competitors.

The next process is that IPOs will be allocated to investors based on the high interests and attention of each stock investor offered. When an investor has the desire to get a large allocation of IPOs shares, then of course the investor has an optimistic sense of the prospects of these

shares. Conversely, the underwriter must offer IPOS shares at a profitable price (bargaining power) to the investor in an effort to persuade or interest it to participate in bookbuilding and sharing information. Therefore, there is generally underpricing the IPOS shares. This underpricing is reflected in the price surge on the first day of stock traded to the public (Bodie et al., 2019). Thus, investors are one of the parties who also played a role in determining the price of the first stock. The study of underpricing levels and stock market prices connected with information on prospectus is interesting for financial analysis to empirically evaluate investor behavior in making investment decisions in the capital market both short -term, medium term or long -term for the long term. The analysis sometimes focuses research on prospectus information related to financial and non -financial information.

The results of research from various researchers who are inconsistent with each other who encourage researchers to do it again research. From various inconsistent researchers results can be explained as in Sri Winarsih Ramadana (2018), Financial Leverage (Debt to Equity Ratio/DER) has a positive effect on underpricing, profitability (return on equity/ROE), the reputation of the authorities of emissions, company age and company size negatively affect the underpricing. Other research results also show that financial leverage, profitability (ROE), the reputation of underwriters, company age and company size affect the underpricing.

In the research results of Andrew Budiman (2018), that the profitability of ROA, ROE, has a significant effect on underpricing. Other results by Himawan Budi Kuncoro, Rossje V Suryaputri (2019), Underwriter Reputation, Return on Equity (ROE), Company Size significantly influenced underpricing. Mohammad T, Nurmatias and Wahyudi (2019), that the results of his research Return on Equity (ROE), Earnings Per Share (EPS) affect the positive correlation on abnormal returns. Companies that make the first public offer in Martha Rianty N, and Dwi Riana. (2020), underwriter reputation, auditor's reputation, leverage has no significant effect on underpricing. Jenniari Shella Damanik, Ferikawita M. Sembiring (2020), profitability (ROA), underwriter reputation significantly influenced underpricing, while Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), the current ratio had no significant effect on underpricing.

In the research results of Debi Carolina (2020), Current Ratio, Return on Equity (ROE) have an insignificant effect on underpricing. In An Nisa Diah Isnaeni, Najmudin, & Intan Shafi (2020), underwriter, profitability (ROE), leverage significant and positive correlation on underpricing. Ariyanto, Sri Hasnawati, & Ernie Hendrawaty (2020), underwriter's reputation, company age has no significant effect on shares underpricing, while company size, profitability (ROA) has a significant effect with a negative correlation on shares underpricing. Jeny Nurcahyani & Ati Harianti. (2021), the reputation of underwriters, ROA and DAR significantly influenced underpricing, company size had no effect on underpricing. Nanda Kusuma Wardana, Acep Suherman, & Elan Eriswanto (2021), ROA and DER have a significant effect on underpricing. Erly Mulyani & Rahmah Maulidya (2021), KAP's reputation, company size, company age and profitability, have a significant effect on underpricing. underpricing. (Return on Equity/ROE) an insignificant effect on underpricing. Mutia Agustina, Imawati Yousida (2021), Company Age, Return on Equity/ROE) and Financial Leverage (Debt to Equity Ratio/DER) Partially have a significant effect on shares underpricing.

Other researchers were conducted by Dyan Fajar Mahardika & Fitri Ismiyanti (2021), Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) affected underpricing. Return on Asset (ROA) negatively affects underpricing. Current Raio has a significant effect on underpricing. The company size affects underpricing. Firm age (firm age) affects the underpricing variable. Novellia Dwijaya and Hadi Cahyadi (2021), company size, underwriter's reputation, and company age have a positive and significant effect on underpricing levels, while financial leverage (Debt to Equity Ratio/DER) and capital market conditions do not significantly affect the underpricing level. Farichah, F. (2018), Profit Management and Reputation of Insurance Corporations and Auditors affect underpricing. Sparta, S., & Firdaus, H. (2023), earnings management has a significant negative effect on Underpricing IPO. The company's size has a significant positive effect on Underpricing IPOs, ownership concentration does not affect the IPO, and institutional ownership does not strengthen the relationship between earnings management and Underpricing IPOs. Natural, E. (2021), earnings management has a significant effect with a positive correlation on underpricing and return stocks. Lizińska, J., & Czapiewski, L. (2018), Pandey, A., & Pattanayak, J. K. (2022), earnings management significantly affects with a positive correlation on underpricing. Ranganathan, K., & Veeraraghavan, M. (2023), voluntary disclosure significantly influences underpricing.

In Natalia Christian and Frecky, (2019), ROE variables, BVS, EPS, Dividend Per Share, Dividend Yield has a significantly influence on stock returns, while variables per, leverage have no significant effect on stock returns. Damanik, Jenniari, and Ferikawita Sembiring (2020), Return on Assets (ROA) and Underwriter's Reputation significantly affect underpricing, while leverage and current ratio have no significant effect on underpricing. Bunduwula, I. A., Hajar, I., & Putera, A. (2023), Leverage has no significant effect on underpricing, and the same thing also happens to the profitability of ROA and Current Ratio. Adiputra, Andre Kussuma, Poly Endrayanto Eko Christmawan, and Angellin Corry Astavia Tlonaen (2023), that Return on Assets (ROA), Earning Per Share (EPS), and Current Ratio (CR) have a significant effect on the negative correlation on underpricing. Marcella, Angelina, and Wawan Andang Saputra (2024), the results of his research prove that there is a significant influence between the reputation of the guarantor of emissions, financial performance, profitability, and financial leverage in partially on underpricing.

HYPOTHESIS

- H₁: Return on Assets (ROA) affects underpricing
- H₂: There is an influence of debt to equity ratio (DER) on underpricing
- H₃: There is an influence of return on equity (ROE) on underpricing
- H₄: Company size (size) affects underpricing
- H₅: Current Ratio (CR) affects underpricing
- H₆: Earnings Management (EM) affects underpricing
- H₇: There is an influence of Company Age (AGE) on Underpricing

- H₈: There is an influence of voluntary disclosure (DI) on underpricing
 H₉: Return on Assets (ROA) affects the stock return
 H₁₀: There is an influence of debt to equity ratio (DER) on stock return
 H₁₁: There is an influence of return on equity (ROE) on stock return
 H₁₂: Company size (size) affects the stock return
 H₁₃: Current Ratio (CR) Affects Stock Return
 H₁₄: Earnings Management (EM) Affects Stock Return
 H₁₅: There is an influence of Company Age (AGE) on stock return
 H₁₆: There is an influence of voluntary disclosure (DI) on stock return
 H₁₇: There is an effect of underpricing (up) on stock return

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach with the analytical method used is multiple linear regression panel data using a combination of time series data series five years or period 2015 - 2019 or 5 years and Cross Section 35 companies selected as research samples. This study uses the object of companies that conduct public offering or conduct an Initial Public Offering (IPOS) at the Indonesia Stock Exchange over the five-year period with a population of 171 companies.

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

No	Variables	Notation	Formulas
1	Return on Asset	ROA _{it}	$\frac{\text{Earnings After Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
2	Leverage	DER _{it}	$\frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$
3	Return on Equity	ROE _{it}	$\frac{\text{Earnings After Tax}}{\text{Total Equity}}$
4	Company Size	CS _{it}	Natural logarithm of total assets
5	Current Ratio	CR _{it}	$\frac{\text{Current Assets}_{it}}{\text{Current Liabilities}_{it}}$
6	Earnings Management	EM _{it}	$\text{DAC} = \frac{\text{TAC}_{i,t}}{\text{TA}_{i,t-1}} - \text{NDA}_{i,t}$
7	Company Age	AGE _{it}	Company from Establishment to IPO
8	Voluntary Disclosure	DI _{it}	n: number of items disclosed by the company k: number of items the company should have disclosed
9	Underpricing	UP _{it}	$\frac{\text{Initial Price}_{it} - \text{Initial Price}_{i(t-1)}}{\text{Initial Price}_{i(t-1)}}$
10	Stock Return	AR _{it}	$\frac{\text{SP}_{it} - \text{SP}_{i(t-1)}}{\text{SP}_{i(t-1)}}$

Multiple Regression Estimates Panel Data

In conducting multiple regression estimation of panel data, it is first ensured that there is a combination of time series data and cross-section data. The approach that can be taken in conducting the analysis between time series data and cross-section data can use the following analysis:

1. Common Effect Model (CEM)
2. Fixed Effect Model (FEM)
3. Random Effect Model (REM)

Model Selection in Testing

The three basic analyses above are used to carry out model suitability testing procedures in order to select the appropriate panel data multiple regression model in the following ways:

Chow Test

F-statistic as a standard used to determine the choice between the Common Effect model or the Fixed Effect model. Acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis is based on the level of $\alpha = 5\%$ on the null hypothesis (H_0) and the alternative hypothesis (H_a).

Each of the two models above will technically compare the calculation of the F-statistic with the F-table. The results of the F count <from the F table will reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and vice versa will accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a).

Thus the appropriate model to be used is the Fixed Effect Model, the decision will be taken otherwise if the results will be different.

Hausman Test

In the direction of Hausman testing, it is intended to determine the choice of Fixed Effect Model or Random Effect Model. The criteria used are the Chi-Square statistical distribution and degree of freedom as much as k with the number of exogenous variables as the basis for testing.

The test will result in accepting the null hypothesis (H_0) and rejecting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) for the next model will be said to be fit and use the Random Effect Model, but on the contrary will use the Fixed Effect Model if the statistical hypothesis rejects the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_a).

Panel Data Regression Model

Structural Equation of Research Model I,

$$UP_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2DER_{it} + \beta_3ROE_{it} + \beta_4CS_{it} + \beta_5CR_{it} + \beta_6EM_{it} + \beta_7AGE_{it} + \beta_8DI_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$i = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots, N ; \quad t = 1,2,\dots\dots\dots T$

Structural Equation of Research Model II,

$$AR_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 ROA_{it} + \beta_2 DER_{it} + \beta_3 ROE_{it} + \beta_4 CS_{it} + \beta_5 CR_{it} + \beta_6 EM_{it} + \beta_7 AGE_{it} + \beta_8 DI_{it} + \beta_9 UP_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, N$; $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$

Where:

UP	=	Underpricing		ε	=	Error component
ROA	=	Return On Assets		β	=	Slope
DER	=	Debt to Equity Ratio		α	=	Intercept
ROE	=	Return On Equity		N	=	Number of Observations
CS	=	Company Size		T	=	Lots of time
CR	=	Current Ratio		NxT	=	Number of Panel Data
EM	=	Earnings Management				
AGE	=	Company Age				
DI	=	Voluntary Disclosure				
AR	=	Stock Return				

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Descriptive Statistics and Model Conformity Test

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	DER	ROE	SIZE	CR	EM	AGE	DI	UP	AR
Mean	6.926435	1.274159	0.163008	27.34502	2.435715	0.466462	22.91429	0.525184	0.779148	0.452159
Median	5.646381	0.985251	0.127806	28.03248	1.701075	0.415087	19.00000	0.544276	0.009524	0.061983
Maximum	84.19089	7.117488	1.687096	30.60577	14.41194	0.999719	55.00000	0.999071	26.66667	9.250000
Minimum	0.019529	0.029921	0.000232	18.43375	0.006975	0.013738	0.000000	0.005661	-0.990000	-0.770000
Std. Dev.	7.964440	1.184792	0.214176	2.678590	2.490259	0.281820	16.28830	0.294720	4.460976	1.335915
Skewness	5.793310	2.103851	4.716599	-1.855509	2.611231	0.319440	0.432536	-0.103512	5.624683	4.343991
Kurtosis	53.05932	9.244717	30.97061	6.107833	10.52566	1.891416	1.800523	1.725037	32.77748	25.14881
Sum	1212.126	222.9777	28.52638	4785.379	426.2502	81.63085	4010.000	91.90714	136.3510	79.12788
Sum Sq. Dev.	11037.22	244.2493	7.981627	1248.423	1079.042	13.81951	46163.71	15.11362	3462.653	310.5325
Observations	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Source: Processed data

Endogenous Variables: Underpricing and Stock Return in the Suitability Test of Research Model-1 & Research Model-2.

Table 3: Research Model Suitability Testing-1

No.	Statistical Hypothesis Test	Test Results	Model Fit
1	Chow-Test, Ho : F prob. Test > α 0,05 (Suitable Model = CEM) Ha : F prob. Test < α 0,05 (Suitable Model = FEM)	(Common Effect vs Fixed Effect) F prob. = 0.0309 < α 0.05	Fixed Effect
2	Hausman Test, Ho : F prob. Test > α 0,05 (Suitable Model = REM) Ha : F prob. Test < α 0,05 (Suitable Model = FEM)	(Fixed Effect vs Random Effect) Cross-section random prob. = 0.0432 < α 0.05	Fixed Effect

Source: Processed data

Table 4: Research Model Suitability Testing-2

No.	Statistical Hypothesis Test	Test Results	Model Fit
1	Chow-Test, Ho : F prob. Test > α 0,05 (Suitable Model = CEM) Ha : F prob. Test < α 0,05 (Suitable Model = FEM)	(Common Effect vs Fixed Effect) F prob. = 0.0359 < α 0.05	Fixed Effect
2	Hausman Test, Ho : F prob. Test > α 0,05 (Suitable Model = REM) Ha : F prob. Test < α 0,05 (Suitable Model = FEM)	(Fixed Effect vs Random Effect) Cross-section random prob. = 0.0184 < α 0.05	Fixed Effect

Source: Processed data

Table 5: Endogenous Variable: UP

Total pool (balanced) observations: 175

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.779148	0.362146	3.873312	0.0000
ROA	-1.496835	0.043792	-2.625347	0.0097
DER	4.573577	0.054238	2.108512	0.0138
ROE	-4.479236	0.036532	-2.182294	0.0309
SIZE	-3.723674	0.046329	-3.361743	0.0320
CR	-2.914843	0.124328	-2.454135	0.0483
AGE	-2.253776	0.039345	-3.224935	0.0270
EM	-5.933386	0.035421	-2.507077	0.0129
DI	-1.685974	0.024765	-3.373928	0.0018
Adjusted R-squared	0.652236			
F-statistic	25.4278; Prob (F-statistic): 0.00000			

Source: Processed data

Table 6: Endogenous Variable: AR

Total pool (balanced) observations: 175

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.593796	6.901837	2.100257	0.0132
ROA	0.008577	0.018740	3.057676	0.0479
DER	-0.207161	0.144377	-2.434864	0.0137
ROE	0.195342	0.702836	2.277934	0.0215
SIZE	0.458513	0.293611	2.561632	0.0308
CR	0.033343	0.068576	3.486224	0.0076
AGE	0.244044	0.093785	2.602178	0.0303
EM	0.344835	0.401087	2.859751	0.0015
DI	0.776060	0.420326	3.846328	0.0071
UP	-1.969164	2.693491	-3.731083	0.0460
Adjusted R-squared	0.692391			
F-statistic	40.9879; Prob (F-statistic): 0.0000			

Source: Processed data

- 1: Return on assets profitability significantly affects underpricing with negative correlation (Table5).
- 2: Capital structure significantly affects and has a positive correlation on underpricing. (Table5).
- 3: Return on Equity profitability significantly affects underpricing with negative correlation (Table5).
- 4: Company size significantly affects underpricing with a negative correlation (Table 5).
- 5: Current Ratio has a significant effect on underpricing with a negative correlation (Table 5).
- 6: Company Age significantly affects and has a negative correlation on underpricing. (Table 5).
- 7: Earnings Management significantly affects and has a negative correlation on underpricing. (Table5).
- 8: Voluntary disclosure has a significant effect on underpricing and negative correlation. (Table5).
- 9: Profitability Return on Assets significantly affects Stock Return with positive correlation (Table6).
- 10: Capital structure significantly affects and has a positive correlation on stock return. (Table6).
- 11: Profitability Return on Equity significantly affects Stock Return with positive correlation (Table6).

- 12: Company size significantly affects Stock Return with positive correlation (Table 6).
- 13: Current Ratio has a significant effect on stock return with positive correlation (Table 6).
- 14: Company Age significantly affects and has a positive correlation on Stock Return. (Table 6).
- 15: Earnings Management significantly affects and has a positive correlation on Stock Return. (Table 6).
- 16: Voluntary disclosure has a significant effect on Stock Return and is positively correlated. (Table6).
- 17: Underpricing has a significant effect on Stock Return and is negatively correlated. (Table6).

B. Discussion

This study uses the endogenous Underpricing variable in the first research model where the result is that all exogenous variables used can explain their effect on endogenous variables with the highest level of sensitivity in the earnings management variable and negative correlation.

These results can be explained that the higher Earnings Management which has the potential towards profit engineering, the market conditions increasingly do not give appreciation to the issuer securities.

In the results of the study in the second research model, showing the same results as the first research model, all exogenous variables can explain their effect on the highest stock Return endogenous variable with the highest level of sensitivity in the underpricing variable with a negative correlation.

These results can be explained that the lower the price of stock securities in the primary market, the market appreciation of the prices in the secondary market will be beneficial for capital market participants.

The use of underpricing as an intervening variable in this study can function to mediate the influence of exogenous variables on the endogenous stock return variable, so that the market reaction will contribute to stock returns that depend on underpricing on the primary market.

CONCLUSION

Findings: Research gives the conclusion that underpricing as an intervening variable can explain its effect significantly on stock return which means that market reactions will depend on the occurrence of underpricing in the primary market.

Apart from that, that among the exogenous variables used and the highest level of sensitivity is in the earnings management variable in the first research model while underpricing is in the second research model.

This can be a suggestion for further researchers and especially for the company's management authority regarding the importance of paying attention to the Earnings Management and Underpricing variables as key variables by capital market players in the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

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